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DIASPORA AND TRANSNATIONAL IMAGINARIES IN CHIMAMANDA NGOZI

ADICHIE'S *THE THING AROUND YOUR NECK*

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Abstract

This paper explores Adichie's conception of émigré Nigerians within the diasporic paradigm and particularly in love relationships while living in the United States of America. Adichie deploys her stories to examine the complexities that characterize immigrant life in America and the many shenanigans that are adopted by immigrants as a strategy of survival including sham marriages so as to get the green card and to evade the wrath of the American immigration authorities. Adichie explodes the myth of America as the promised land of the earth that flows with milk and honey and holds the prospect of solving the problems of emigrants as soon as they set foot on its soil. This is because the realities that immigrants face in America sharply contrast with the images that are painted of it. Nigerian immigrants in Adichie's stories face all kinds of harrowing experiences such as racial discrimination, joblessness, immigration problems, alienation as well as getting lost in the vast American labyrinth. The paper concludes that contrary to the widely touted perceptions of America as the land of limitless opportunity, immigrants still struggle to eke out a meaningful existence and are confined to the fringes of American life.

KEYWORDS: Diaspora, émigré Nigerians, emigrants, American labyrinth, sham marriages

Introduction

The diaspora has been a dominant trope in contemporary African literature over a considerable period. Chimamanda Adichie turned her attention to diaporic issues following her landmark publication of *The Thing Around Your Neck* (2009). Adichie was one of the first contemporary Nigerian writers to turn attention to the diaspora after a long period of what was considered African writers' obsession with our cultural past. At the turn of the century, Charles Nnolin gave the charge to the African writer that "the 21st century offers the African writer opportunities to carve out a new humanism devoid of the complexes of the 20th century that made him as defensive as a second-class citizen of the world. The African writer in the 21st century should forget the complexes of the past and be more imaginatively progressive and expansive" (4). As though responding to this charge, Adichie was the first to turn attention to the issues of the Nigerian diaspora. Tunca Duria highlights this fact in his article titled "Of French Fries and Cookies: Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's Diasporic Short Fiction" when he writes:

The quest for Nigerian identity by writers came full circle with the arrival of Third Generation writers like Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, Teju Cole and several others who have penned down their experiences of living in a foreign country with a firsthand description and originality.... While Adichie too is a resident of the USA on academic purpose, she is entitled to be listed as a diaspora writer with the arrival of her short story volume *The Thing Around Your Neck* and her novel *Americanah* as both these works deal with the lives of Nigerian citizens in America (292).

Tunca's words above appropriately confer on Adichie the tag of a diasporic writer. And Tunca is not the only one who shares this opinion. A vast array of scholars of Adichie's

works observe that *The Thing Around Your Neck* marked the diasporic turning point in the vision of Adichie as a writer. In this collection of shorts stories Adichie interrogates the myth of America as the promised land of the earth by bringing to the front burner some of the challenges that Nigerian immigrants face in their quest for the Golden Fleece in the United States of America.

Diasporic Ambivalence and the Quest for Assimilation

Chimamanda Adichie devotes several of her dozen short stories in *The Thing Around Your Neck* to the exploration of the complex matrix of the Diaspora and the array of attending tropes within the transnationalist milieu. The first story of the expatriate experience titled “Imitation” deals with the protagonist’s strong desire to return to Nigeria after a period in America with the children; while the husband Obiora stays in Nigeria for his business and to nurse his political contacts. At first Nkem is excited like every other intending migrant, with the prospect of going to live in America:

...when she had come to America to have the baby, she had been proudly excited because she has married into the coveted league, the Rich Nigerian men who sent their Wives to America to Have Their Babies League (26).

Nkem and Obiora have bought a plush house in Philadelphia where Nkem lives with their two children while Obiora lives in their Lagos home to pursue his businesses and his political engagements. Their children Adanna and Okey, three years apart are enrolled to go to school in America. The desperation by many immigrants to get integrated into the mainstream of the American society is exhibited by Nkem as she wants their children to imitate white children:

She did not mind that her accent, her foreignness, made her seem helpless to them. She liked them and their lives. Lives Obiora often called “plastic”. Yet she knew he, too, wanted the children to be like their neighbours...(24).

Nkem’s attitude above speaks of the internal crisis of identity that plagues many immigrants. In their bid to douse the effect of cultural alienation, they become subservient to the foreign culture and slavishly absorb it in a desperate quest for integration. It is curious why Obiora would decide that his family should live in America while he lives by himself in Nigeria. This is made the more worrying owing to the fact that Obiora’s reason for remaining in Nigeria is because business thrives more in Nigeria. This is confirmed by another woman in a conversation with Nkem:

Our men like to keep us here, she had told Nkem, they visit for business and vacations, they leave us and the children with big houses and cars, they get us house girls from Nigeria who we don’t have to pay any outrageous American wages, they say business is better in Nigeria and all that (28).

The question is the rationale for going or sending a family to live in America if the business even thrives more and is better in Nigeria. Therefore, could it be that going to live in America such as Obiora has decided of his family is merely to satisfy an inner craving of an expatriate existence? All things considered, one worries about the compulsive inclination or craze to live in America if the motivation is not a foray in search of the Golden Fleece and greener pastures as it is generally the case.

Adichie presents a contrasting trope in the diaspora dialectic as could be seen in the decision of Obiora to send his wife to stay in America while he remains in Nigeria. This scenario rips through the superior/inferior schema in the relationship between Africa and America and nullifies the notion that opportunities can only be found in America as opposed

to the perception of Nigeria as an arid land devoid of opportunities. In spite of the seeming lush and plush comforts that America presents, Nkem is struck by a gnawing nostalgia and she longs to return home. She feels terribly homesick and misses home and virtually everything: “She does miss home, though, her friends, the cadence of Igbo and Yoruba and pidgin English spoken around her. And when the snow covers the yellow fire hydrants on the street, she misses Lagos sun that glares down even when it rains” (37).

Caught in the throes of identity crisis, alienation and loneliness coupled with her husband’s adulterous liaisons with women back home in Nigeria, Nkem decides to quit America to move back to Nigeria: “We are moving back at the end of school year. We are moving back to live in Lagos. We are moving back”. She speaks slowly, to convince him, to convince herself as well...” (41). Adichie in this story addresses the duality and double-consciousness that plagues immigrants as they always seem to be torn between a life in America and returning home. This double-consciousness or psychic split underlies diasporic identity. Nkem’s return blots out the vainglorious hype of America and its utopic promise. Here, Adichie deals a shattering blow to the pretences of a glossy American life and Nkem’s return to Nigeria proves the futility of this utopia and recasts the narrative to mean that Nigeria could also hold the chance for a better life like the proverbial land of opportunity.

Sham Marriages and the American Utopia

“The Arrangers of Marriage” deals with a marriage arranged by people who believe that life in America is such a bed of roses. Uncle Ike and Aunty Ada, owing to their indebtedness and precarious economic situation in Nigeria, have arranged for Chinaza, an orphan, to marry a doctor she has never met from America. This loveless union is consummated in the most bizarre manner: “I wanted a Nigerian wife and my mother said you were a good girl, quiet. She said you might even be a virgin...” I was happy when I saw your

picture” (184). Chinaza’s arranged marriage to Ofodile is conceived as a contractual union that is meant to liberate her from the shackles of poverty and that of her family: “A doctor in America”. He said, beaming. “What could be better? Ofodile’s mother was looking for a wife for him; she was very concerned that he would marry an American” (170). To Uncle Ike and Aunt Ada’s belief, even ordinary people living in America have a good life going for them much less a medical doctor who in their view would confer her (Chinaza) with all the comforts of this life in matrimony. However, it is appropriate to observe that Ofodile’s desire to marry a Nigerian wife bespeaks alienation in a society that keeps immigrants on the cultural sidelines without affording them participation in the mainstream of affairs.

Ofodile and his stay in America is representative of the desperation many intending immigrants exhibit just to gain entry into America where they believe that all their problems would just be melted by some magic wand. Before his marriage to Chinaza, he had arranged a marriage with an American lady as a leeway to obtaining a “green card” in order to gain entry into the land of opportunity: “The American woman I married to get a green card is making trouble....our divorce was almost final, but, not completely, before I married you in Nigeria. Just a minor thing, but she found out about it and now she’s threatening to report me to Immigration. She wants more money” (182).

It is apparent that Ofodile is in a dire dilemma. He is unhinged and must be frantic enough before he is thrown out of America on account of improper status with Immigration. His dilemma is also representative of a vast array of cases where many immigrants on doing everything possible to get to America including sham marriages face the threat of deportation as “*persona non grata*”. The phenomenon of incomplete papers and improper immigration status is a perennial problem among immigrants which make them stand the risk of repatriation.

In “The Arrangers of Marriage”, Adichie adequately highlights the issues of diasporic identities and acculturation. She harps on the phenomenon of loss of identity by immigrants in their bid to be assimilated into the mainstream socio-cultural milieu. Ofodile is engulfed in the crisis of identity which leads to a total obliteration of every trace of his lingo-cultural identity. It is apparent from the behaviour of Ofodile that the American society treats every other subject as the “other” and their relationship with non-Americans is on the basis of a superior/inferior schema. As a consequence, Ofodile changes his name from Ofodile Udenwa to Dave Bells:

“I’m not called Ofodile here, by the way. I go by Dave,...The last name I use here is different, too. Americans have a hard time with Udenwa, so I changed it You don’t understand how it works in this country. If you want to get anywhere you have to be as mainstream as possible. If not, you will be left by the roadside. You have to use your English name here” (172)

Ofodile loses his identity in the labyrinth of America. It is obvious that the American system presents a make or break scenario for all immigrants. It is either you do it the American way or you are cast out to operate from the fringes of the American utopia. This scenario, put differently could imply that to live and survive in America as an immigrant means that you have to be reconfigured to fit into the American frames. Ofodile insists that his wife must also change her Igbo name to English:

“I never have, my English name is just something on my birth certificate. I have been Chinaza Okafor my whole life”, “you will be used to it, baby”, he said, reaching out to caress my cheek. “You’ll see” when he filled out a social security number application for me the next day, the name he entered in bold letters was AGATHA BELL (173).

The scenario of assuming new names to cope in a society that seemingly has no place for “the exotic other” bespeaks the essentialization of “categories” other than native-born Americans. This also plays to the notes of the racial dialectic within the context of the United States where blacks are victims on the other side of the colour divide.

It is instructive to note that in presenting the identity narrative of diaspora Nigerians and their manner in trying to cope with the throes of displacement, alienation and racial slurs, Adichie seems to be consistent in forging a counter-narrative that repudiates the ascribed notion of America and its ways as inherently superior. Traditionally, Ofodile and Chinaza and many other immigrants, changing and assuming new identities is to fit into the paradigm of a “superior” entity that is America, however, Adichie introduces a new dialectic that counteracts these assumptions. Therefore, Adichie introduces the characters of Nia who is a black American with an African name who is also interested in learning African languages, particularly Igbo: “It’s really pretty. You know, Nia is a Swahili name. I changed my name when I was eighteen. I spent three years in Tanzania. It was fucking Amazing”. Oh, “I said and shook my head; she, a black American, had chosen an African name, while my husband made me change mine to an English one” (180). The character of Nia points to Adichie’s deliberate strategy in forging a counter-hegemonic discourse in the cross-cultural dialectic. Just like Nkem in “Imitation”, who decides to leave America and return to Nigeria at the end of her children’s school year, Chinaza realizes that for her to actualize her dreams of a good life in America as was conceived by the arrangers of her marriage, she decides that she will have to leave her husband Dave Bell so she could come into her own and regain control of her destiny with a green card of her own. Both Nkem and Chinaza lost their identities on a foreign soil and a return to their homeland becomes the ultimate redress to their ordeals.

Diasporic Dystopia and the Dissipation of the American Dream

The eponymous story “The Thing Around Your Neck” is another story that poignantly portrays the paradox of existence in America as an immigrant. According to Kirti, “The Thing Around Your Neck” describes “the tale of Akunna’s American dream and its dissipation” (128). The story is built around a Nigerian girl Akunna who wins a visa lottery to the United States in hope of a better life but ends up in the rude reality of a harrowing experience and difficulty.

Before she departs for the United States, her conception of America is the same as that of all intending migrants: of America being a utopic land of ease, flowing with milk and honey. The family back in Nigeria also thinks that her ‘escape’ to America will mean their escape from poverty: You thought everybody in America had a car and a gun; your uncle and aunts and cousins thought so, too. Right after you won the American visa lottery, they told you: in a month, you will have a big car. Soon, a big house. But don’t buy a gun like those Americans” (115).

Akunna arrives America to a different reality. She discovers that the much touted American dream does not get realized or handed on a golden platter. She even discovers to her surprise that there are poor Americans: “You wanted to write that rich Americans were thin and poor Americans were fat and that many did not have a big house and car” (119). To Akunna, the myth of America as a land paved with gold dissolves soon after her arrival. She does not even have a place upon her arrival and has to put up with a distant relation in an old house in Maine: ‘Your uncle in America, who had put in the names of all your family members for the American visa lottery, said you could live with him until you got on your feet’ (115). Contrary to expectations, Akunna in addition to the absence of a decent job suffers sexual exploitation from the supposed uncle who gives her temporary accommodation and defends his amorous misbehaviour by telling her that America is give and take: “You gave up a lot but you gained a lot too” (116).

Akunna does not only suffer joblessness and exploitation, but her hope of going to school in America is also dashed: “You could not afford to go to school, because now you paid rent for the tiny room with the stained carpet. Besides, the small Connecticut town didn’t have a community college and credits at the state university cost too much. So you went to the public library, you looked up course syllabi and school Websites and read some of the books” (117).

Adichie harps on the withering hardship in Nigeria which pushes young people like Akunna to a foreign land in search of the Golden Fleece. The circumstances of the life at home directly impinge on the lives of immigrants in America. Akunna’s expectations are nearly dashed and she becomes caught in a haunting nostalgia and longing for home:

Sometimes you sat on the lumpy mattress of your twin bed and thought about home-your aunts who hawked dried fish and plantains, cajoling customers to buy and then shouting insults... your friends who had come out to say goodbye before you left, to rejoice because you won the American visa lottery, to confess their envy; your parents who often held hands as they walked to church... your mother whose salary was barely enough to pay your brothers’ fees at the secondary school (118).

Fouad Mami succinctly captures the hardships of immigrants in America thus:

The media-induced opportunities which America seems to offer for Nigerians are processed by these same frustrated Nigerians not as prospects that one can seize and that in due time, coupled with hard work, may lead to some relative success. Instead, they are approached as self-evident truths or facts of nature that guarantee material extrication towards the American heaven (9).

It is Akunna's wish to keep regular correspondence and be updated with the happenings at home but her deprivation and lean existence prevents her. In lieu of the writing home, every month, she would carefully wrap dollars in a brown envelop to send home a large part of her salary. There is a palpable loss of identity for Akunna as she tries to navigate life in America because she would confine her thoughts to herself by neither writing the people at home nor unburdening herself to her colleagues at the restaurant where she works:

Nobody knew where you were because you told no one. Sometimes you felt invisible and tried to walk through your room into the hallway, and when you bumped into the wall, it left bruises on your arm...At Night, something would wrap itself around your neck, something that very nearly choked you before you fell asleep (119).

Through this story, Adichie harps on the post-colonial phenomenon of otherness and the Whites' essentialization of Blacks. For instance, Americans believe that Blacks are savages or perhaps creations of a lesser god judging from their base perception of Africans: "They asked where you learned to speak English and if you had real houses back in Africa and if you'd seen a car before you came to America. They gawped at your hair. Does it stand up or fall down when you take out the braids?" (116). Such a base perception of Blacks reeks of stark essentialization and a crude lump of dignified people as if they were a sub-human category. This kind of base categorization is characteristic of the superior/inferior schema that best describes the relationship between white Americans and hyphenated-Americans and the overarching phenomenon of race. This scenario manifests glaringly when Akunna falls in love with a white American college professor, a relationship seen by many as socially unacceptable merely on account of their skin complexion:

You knew by people's reactions that you two were abnormal...the old white men and women who murmured and glared at him, the black men who shook their heads at you, the black women whose pitying eyes bemoaned your lack of self-esteem, your self-loathing. Or the black women who tried too hard to forgive you, saying a too obvious hi to him, the white men and women who said, "What a good looking pair" (125).

Akunna's experience as it connects her love affairs and dalliance with white Americans in such a racist enclave like America is in so many ways similar to that of Ifemelu in Adichie's *Americanah*. In the same manner that Ifemelu had to grapple with race in her love affair with Curt, so is the scenario with Akunna as she struggles to keep a relationship with the white college professor. In this story, Adichie depicts how the loss of identity, race and the realities of immigrant life impinge on the central character and by extension all expatriates. Ferdinand Asoo sums up the complexities in Akunna's life thus:

"The Thing Around Your Neck" is most typical of these stories that deal with the experience of Nigerians in America. It touches on the false and over-bloated expectations of Nigerians about to move to the United States. The general belief is that of comfort, ease, good houses, good food, plenty of dollars, employment and general economic and social security with additional feelings that excesses will be sent home to augment the conditions of relations at home (16).

The story ends when Akunna finally writes home and receives the shocking news of her father's death. Her father had died for over five months without her knowing about it since she was not able to write back home to keep track of events and happenings. She decides that the ultimate thing or option is for her to return to Nigeria. Just like Ifemelu in

Americanah also decides to return to Nigeria after fifteen years in America, Akunna ultimately returns to Nigeria and is unsure whether she would return to America. The phenomenon of return remains an overarching motif in Adichie's stories. Almost all the protagonists in Adichie's stories who live in America decide that it is better to return to Nigeria. Therefore it is appropriate to observe that the harrowing experiences in the hostland make return to the homeland an ultimate decision. Adichie consequently deconstructs the myth of America as the utopic land flowing with milk and honey and the earthly Eldorado. The traffic back to Africa introduces a curious dynamic to the migration narrative.

Love, Despair and the Search for Diasporic Fraternity

“The Shivering” is the last story in the collection that explores the phenomenon of emigrants to the United States of America. The story deals with the search for fraternity and identity in a foreign land. It harnesses transnational impulses as it connects a fraternal and communal existence in a land that promises more but yields too little. The story opens with Ukamaka, a resident at Princeton University who fearing that a plane crash in Nigeria might have killed her ex-boyfriend Udenna. Chinedu who happens to be Ukamaka’s neighbour comes over and they both pray for the safety of the survivors. Chinedu prays with Ukamaka in a typical pentecostal way that makes her begin to shiver violently. A call from Ukamaka’s mother tells her that Udenna had missed the flight and was not among the people aboard. Her fears are assuaged and she now looks forward to the time both of them will be reunited. The story ends with Ukamaka discovering that Chinedu is not a resident at Princeton as he had claimed but only lived in a friend’s apartment from where he worked in a construction site but has now lost his job. His visa had expired three years ago and would soon be deported back to Nigeria. Ukamaka, moved by fraternal feelings takes him to a catholic church where she introduces him to Father Patrick with the hope that something will be done to avert his deportation. Writing on the significance of this story, Kirti submits that:

Adichie leaves an open ended conclusion to this story of faith and trust which conveys to the readers how, in distress, natives extend a helping hand to each others in America. While there are various cues of disillusionment and deception yet faith shines bright and gives an appropriate ending to the story. It conveys more than meets the eye because it is a tale of finding Nigerian roots in a foreign land where everything seems uncaring, a stranger gives hope and optimism. Adichie’s treatment of the problems of immigrant Nigerians is

definitely novel in the way that she tries to explore the hindsight of the people in Nigeria as well as those settled in America. (134).

As Kirti opines, with these immigrant stories, Adichie opens new vistas and avenues in the field of sharing diaspora experiences and narrates the tales of Nigerian youths who after getting beguiled by the American dream, “embrace irrational choices and confusing them even further all towards dystopic alternatives” (2). With *The Thing Around Your Neck*, Adichie offers an introspection of the choices the young generation of Nigerians make and the kinds of challenges immigration poses before them. (135).

Conclusion

In conclusion, Adichie carves characters that grapple with an array of issues torn between their hostland in America and the homeland back in Africa and are haunted by a kind of ambivalence. Some of these issues range from sham marriages, love, despair, and assimilation to diasporic fraternity and the American utopia.

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